

Article

Trustworthy AI for Whom? GenAI Detection Techniques of Trust Through Decentralized Web3 Ecosystems

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Abstract: As generative AI (GenAI) technologies proliferate, ensuring trust and transparency in digital ecosystems becomes increasingly critical, particularly within democratic frameworks. This article examines decentralized Web3 mechanisms—blockchain, decentralized autonomous organizations (DAOs), and data cooperatives—as foundational tools for enhancing trust in GenAI. These mechanisms are analyzed within the framework of the EU’s AI Act and the Draghi Report, focusing on their potential to support content authenticity, community-driven verification, and data sovereignty. Based on a systematic policy analysis, this article proposes a multi-layered framework to mitigate the risks of AI-generated misinformation. Specifically, as a result of this analysis, it identifies and evaluates seven detection techniques of trust stemming from the action research conducted in the Horizon Europe Lighthouse project called ENFIELD: (i) federated learning for decentralized AI detection, (ii) blockchain-based provenance tracking, (iii) zero-knowledge proofs for content authentication, (iv) DAOs for crowdsourced verification, (v) AI-powered digital watermarking, (vi) explainable AI (XAI) for content detection, and (vii) privacy-preserving machine learning (PPML). By leveraging these approaches, the framework strengthens AI governance through peer-to-peer (P2P) structures while addressing the socio-political challenges of AI-driven misinformation. Ultimately, this research contributes to the development of resilient democratic systems in an era of increasing technopolitical polarization.

Keywords: generative AI; decentralization; Web3; trustworthy AI; blockchain; DAOs; data cooperatives; big data; detection techniques; democracy

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1. Introduction: Trustworthy AI for Whom?

The rise of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has introduced transformative tools capable of generating complex, human-like content in text, imagery, and sound [1,2]. While these technologies hold vast potential for innovation across industries, they also pose significant risks related to trust, authenticity, and accountability. As the European Commission has globally advanced the AI Act framework to regulate and assure “trustworthy AI”, the question of clarifying for whom it should be trustworthy becomes increasingly urgent [3,4]. This inquiry is foundational, especially as GenAI tools permeate sensitive sectors